

Privatization and Family Welfare: A Study on Primary School Teachers in Tehsil Bhawana District Chiniot

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Abstract

Privatization disturb the sense of communal and association among teachers. Public schools conventionally adoptive a supportive environment where teachers effectively utilized their available resources to enhance the quality of education. Privatization of the public sector cause many obstacles for students as well as teachers which affect the standard of education. The main aim of the study is to identify the effect of privatization and family welfare: a study on primary school teachers in tehsil Bhawana district Chiniot. The current study “privatization and family welfare: a study on primary school teachers” was conducted in tehsil Bhawana District Chiniot. The study was descriptive and survey type in nature. The study was quantitative type in nature. According to DDEO, there were total 31 schools in tehsil Bhawana, (privatization scheme) in these schools there were 155 teachers currently working. A sample size of 109 was selected through www.surveysystem.com with confidence level 95% and confidence interval 5. A well-structured questionnaire was developed according to the study’s objectives for data collection from selected respondents.

INTRODUCTION

Privatization in education means handing over the ownership and management of the schools from the government to the organizations. This involves starting private schools and allowing private sector to manage the schools (Hu *et al.*, 2024). The partnerships between schools and private sectors can improve the education. The main goal is to bring the efficiency, creativity and resources of the private sectors to improve the learning outcomes (Warner, 2024).

Public schools may experience poor funding, lack of facilities and less number of teachers. Privatization can help these issues by providing better resources and new teaching methods. Schools can make the environment suitable for the learners according to their needs. They can also provide the high quality of educational system to make students better in academic performance. Private sectors also encourage competition in school's performance results (Joachim and Schneiker, 2022). Competition in schools plays a big role in their educational services. Private schools can help the students who have no access to the education in their areas. There must be rules to make sure students have equal opportunities in their schools (Fjellman and Haley, 2023).

Teachers in private schools are often dismissed by the lower percentage of students and feedback from parents. They work more to keep everything perfect for their job. These kinds of situations can lead to teachers' mental health disturbed. Schools should relieve the teachers from over workload, so they can teach in a positive environment. Private schools prioritize the money which means fewer teachers and overcrowded students in classes (Martindale, 2022). This is the negative effect when teacher student interaction is ignored due to the overcrowded classes. Students from poor backgrounds might face hardships when the outsourced system does not address their needs. Teachers

cannot interact with individuals. They are much more responsible than teaching. They have to check every student's progress in detail and have knowledge about their activities in the schools. The privatization of schools ultimately effects the educational outcomes and teaching pattern in the class room which ultimately affects the students learning (Pineda *et al.*, 2022).

Private organizations taking control means new resources and educational strategies implemented for the teachers and learners. This means teachers might experience the difficulty in teaching due to unfamiliarity with the latest syllabus. Students may not learn more effectively in their studies due to this reason (Noori, 2023). The administration rules for teachers can influence teacher's behavior. When school emphasizes proper discipline and fair rules teachers might act better. Excessive strictness could make teachers feel stifled and less willing to do their job. School management really affects the students' academic behavior as well (Amin and Cochrane, 2024).

Privatization has significantly increased the workload for the primary teachers. Teachers in private schools do more work other than their usual routines. Such as arranging extra activities, detailed reports and staying in touch with students' parents to make sure they are satisfied or not. They also learn the teaching methods on their own for better performance in the class (Creagh *et al.*, 2023). Private schools may have fewer staff due to their lower pay rate. Teachers handle the large number of classes and teach multiple subjects. They cannot focus on each student. They manage discipline in class and attract the new students for admissions by giving the higher percentages of the students (Basu, 2024).

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Privatization is often help in reshaping the role of teachers at school level, modify their

teaching styles, professional identity and overall school culture by using the advance technologies by introducing the performance metrics, competitive environment and introducing the market driving policies that help in improving the quality of education and improving the cognitive ability of the students at school level. For teachers it is quite important to work in such a hectic working environment which may influence their job security, increase workload and commitment and motivation with their work. The current study will explore the impact of school privatization on teacher and their family welfare. The current study will explore the employment outlines, incomes, and economic prospects, which directly disturb families. The study on the privatization impacts economic security for families which helps policymakers to discourse potential disparities that may arise from such alterations. The study will also reveal the solution of such issues faced by the teachers regarding their job security and impact on student's education. The study results help the policy makers and educational stakeholders to understand the impact of privatization on overall wellbeing of teachers and students.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Thompson *et al.* (2022) mentioned that the big change teachers face is the expectation of having the knowledge about the new technology. They also learn the latest modern technologies on their own for the better performance of the students. They have to learn about this after their working hours, which makes their day more hectic. Added responsibilities can leave teachers feeling stressed and overworked. They do not have the time for their families due to their hectic schedule. Schools should set clear goals and monitor the progress of teachers. Organizations should balance the profits with responsibility to provide the fair treatment to

the teachers.

Outsourcing schools can only help students in their accomplishments. It is fundamental to focus on teachers' requirements over benefits of schools and guarantee each teacher gets the opportunity they deserve

Hogan *et al.* (2022) discussed that private schools focus more on teaching qualities to stay competitive with other sectors. They may also offer workshops, training programs for their teachers. They can learn new teaching methods, use technology in lessons and stay updated about the new trends. Schools who have high approaches and standards can do this for their institutions. Schools prioritize professional development for better performance of their students. Some private schools invite the professionals in their schools to address the educational experiences. This can affect the students mind as well. Teachers get the knowledge from their experiences in their own routines. Schools who have low budgets barely offer few programs and inconsistent support for their teachers.

Falkensjö and Olsson (2022) described that privatization in schools requires careful planning to guarantee positive results for students. Clear guidelines are essential to adjust outsourced administrations with educational goals. Administration should focus on primary teachers' activities and guaranteeing seniors to fulfill guidelines with responsibility. Agreements and regular assessments can assist with maintaining the trust among schools and teachers. The outsource services offer new insights which will help to create strategies that balance the teacher's efforts with students' academic excellence.

Kilag *et al.* (2022) stated that educators might face an over workload due to their hectic routines. Teachers manage their class tasks like managing records, maintaining the reports, and parent meetings. Teachers also handle the students' behavior and their

activities. With teaching duties, they can also manage to give their time in lesson planning. Teachers also feel stress when they do not meet performance goals like test scores. It can lead to long hours and create hassle in maintaining work-life balance.

Ali *et al.* (2023) elaborated that many teachers are concerned about the disadvantages of privatization. Test scores and students' regular enrollment is the common worry. Teachers focus on the given targets and learn about the new methods. Teachers also get pressured when they have to be strict to the rules in the classroom. This limitation has a negative effect on their capabilities. Teachers also feel less secure in privatized schools. These issues have a significant impact on the student's mental health. It can make it hard for them to focus on their work. Privatization can bring different rules for primary teachers which make it hard for them.

Rasmitadila *et al.* (2023) concluded that system of privatization changes the school system of education and teaching. Public schools focus on the students all aspects of education, that helps them to grow academically, socially and emotionally. The privatized schools focus often on achieving academic results and meeting the goals like increasing student enrollment. They focus more on their school standards rather than the individual's capabilities. They do not prioritize the other subjects like art and physical education. This limitation can affect the student's opportunities to explore their interests other than academic subjects.

Inganah *et al.* (2023) elaborated that performance goals should focus on the overall growth of the students, not only their test scores. This approach would help lower teachers stress and create a balance between work and their personal lives. Organizations should also notice the individual's capability other than their academic performance. Privatized schools can create a healthier environment. Another step is offering better

professional development. Organizations should arrange regular training programs to teach the new teaching methods to students. Private schools should arrange the workshops and different courses on topics like classroom management, handling student's emotions and building leadership skills. These programs should be available for all teachers. They also ensure that each teacher has access to the programs.

Elbanna and Armstrong (2024) described that private organizations would not put inclusivity first, which could leave primary school teachers lose their teaching professional development. Focus on private schools can also change how their teachers view their roles for their professional identity. Teachers cannot see the individual growth in studies, they just maintain the school standard with high test scores. Educators feel demotivated because of the strict rules given by the authorities. This lack of connection creates difficulties in students and teacher's relationships.

Janssen *et al.* (2024) mentioned that primary school teachers have experienced different kinds of feelings for privatization. Teachers are aware of the privileges and overload of work in schools. Some teachers think they can get more freedom and more benefits. Some feel the extra work and long hours of hectic schedule for them. Private schools allow teachers to do their work on their own, so they create their own lesson plans and try new teaching methods. Students also get noticed by the teachers. Latest technologies help students to get more knowledge about the new modern resources.

METHODOLOGY

The study was descriptive and survey type in nature. The study was quantitative type in nature. According to DDEO, there were total 31 schools in tehsil Bhawana, (privatization scheme) in these schools there were 155 teachers currently working. A sample size of

109 was selected through www.surveysystem.com with confidence level 95% and confidence interval 5. A well-structured questionnaire was developed according to the study's objectives for data collection from selected respondents.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The discussion section seeks to identify any discrepancies between the two studies with regard to different geographic regions or to compare the results of the current research with those of the earlier study. The discussion part facilitates comprehension of the differences between the study's results and those of earlier research on the same subject but carried out at a different time.

Effects of Privatization on living and overall well-being of Teachers

Outsourced schools may not provide the same benefits to students from poor backgrounds. Those who require additional support may fall behind if the emphasis is shifted to high-achieving pupils in an effort to raise overall scores. Learning can be disrupted and performance impacted by frequent changes in policies and teaching personnel (Joseph *et al.*, 2024).

Table 1. Distribution of respondents regarding mean and Std. Deviation of positive effects of privatization

Positive effects	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
Private sector produce more rivalries instructors	4.11	1.13	1
Teachers improved their efficiency in private sector due to privatization	4.03	1.26	2
Privatization	3.72	1.17	3

increase competition by introducing advance teaching technology			
Reduction of the demand for government resources in private sector due to privatization	3.53	1.31	4
Teachers enhance competition and stronger financial health after privatization	2.37	1.55	5

Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

Table 4.7 summarize the mean score, standard deviation and rank order for each statement regarding positive effects of privatization on living and overall well-being of teachers. "Private sector produce more rivalries instructors" ranks 1st, with the highest mean of 4.11 and standard deviation 1.13, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards strongly agree. "Teachers improved their efficiency in private sector due to privatization" rank second, with mean 4.03 and standard deviation 1.26, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. "Privatization increase competition by introducing advance teaching technology" ranks third, with mean 3.72 and standard deviation 1.17, indicating that respondents are lying between neutral and agree but tending towards agree. "Reduction of the demand for government resources in private sector due to privatization" ranks forth, with mean score of 3.53 and standard deviation 1.31, indicating that respondents are lying between neutral and

agree but tending towards agree."Teachers enhance competition and stronger financial health after privatization" ranks fifth, with a mean score 2.37 and standard deviation 1.55, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards strongly disagree.

The study results were same as Shmaryahu-Yeshurun (2024) who described that the way new management handles staffing will have a big impact. It can hinder progress and prioritizing learning outcomes, when ignoring a balanced ratio. It guarantees successful outcomes, careful planning and an emphasis on keeping class sizes manageable are essential. The private organizations manage teacher hiring and classroom sizes responsibly determine whether student achievement rises or falls.

Negative effects of Privatization on living and overall well-being of Teachers

There are worries that employing outside providers might result in students receiving less individualized attention. Teachers may feel under pressure to follow the strict company policies, which could limit their creativity in the classroom. Students' sense of connection to their teachers and lessons may be impacted by this way. The availability of extracurricular and co-curricular activities for students may alter when schools hire outside organizations to run their operations. These businesses occasionally provide more funds and resources, allowing a wider variety of events, such as clubs, music, and sports. Students can learn new skills and explore their interests with this support (Williams, 2022).

Table 2. Distribution of respondents regarding negative effects of privatization

Negative effects of privatization	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
Privatized schools can	4.11	1.04	1

lead to longer hours for teachers			
Lack of funding for professional development opportunities	3.88	1.11	2
Privatization had more selective in their student admissions	3.86	1.18	3
Privatization focus on standardized testing and market-driven outcomes	3.78	1.17	4
Privatized schools may face pressure to prioritize academic outcomes	2.86	1.49	5

Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

Table 4.8 summarize the mean score, standard deviation and rank order for each statement regarding negative effects of privatization on living and overall well-being of teachers. "Privatized School can lead to longer hours for teachers" ranks first, with mean score 4.11 and standard deviation 1.04, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards strong agreement. "Lack of funding for professional development opportunities" rank second, with mean score of 3.88 and standard deviation 1.11, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. "Privatization had more selective in their student admissions" ranks 3rd, with mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation 1.18, indicating that respondent are generally lying between neutral and agree but tending

towards agree. "Privatization focus on standardized testing and market-driven outcomes" ranks 4th, with mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation 1.17, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. "Privatized school may face pressure to prioritize academic outcomes" ranks 5th, with mean score of 2.86 and standard deviation 1.49, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards strongly disagreement. The study results were same as Crawford (2024) who explained that there may be drawbacks as well. Some activities might be reduced if the focus changes to academics and profit. And not every student may have equal access to these programs, particularly if their backgrounds differ. The impact varies according to the quality of the change management.

Impact of Privatization on overall well-being of teacher's Family

Private operators may prioritize financial gain over academic excellence, according to critics. This could lead to cost-cutting strategies that impact the overall learning experience, like hiring teachers with lower qualifications or cutting back on necessary resources. This arrangement may not benefit students in underprivileged communities equally (Mahmud, 2021). Some students may be at a disadvantage if educational differences increase due to a lack of accountability. Since external management might not always be in line with regional educational objectives, questions are also raised regarding the consistency of teaching quality (Sorensen., 2021).

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents regarding impact of Privatization on overall well-being of Teacher's family

Impact of privatization on overall well-being of	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
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teacher's family			
Teachers family in private sector faced financial tension in household tasks	4.22	1.06	1
No special quota for their childcare and their upbringings	3.86	1.20	2
Teachers families had fewer resources for house rent allowance	3.84	1.24	3
Limited health benefits	3.81	1.19	4
Limited educational opportunities for teacher's children	3.77	1.19	5
Potential tuition discounts or scholarships	3.52	1.31	6
Teachers in private sector has less time spent with family	2.82	1.51	7

Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

Table 4.9 summarize the mean score, standard deviation and rank order for each statement regarding impact of privatization on overall well-being of teachers family. "Teachers family in private sector faced financial tension in household task" rank first, with mean score of 4.22 and standard deviation 1.06, indicating that respondent are generally

tending towards agree. "No special quota for their child care and their upbringing" ranks second, with mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation 1.20, indicating that respondents are tending towards agree. "Teachers family had fewer resources for house-rent allowance" ranks 3rd, with mean score of 3.84 and standard deviation 1.24, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. "Limited health benefits" ranks fourth, with mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation 1.19, indicating that respondents are generally lying between neutral and agree but tending towards agree. "Limited educational opportunities for teachers children" ranks 5th, with mean score of 3.77 and standard deviation 1.19, indicating that respondents are lying between neutral and agree but tending towards agree. "Potential tuition discounts or scholarships" ranks 6th, with mean score of 3.52 and standard deviation 1.31, indicating that respondents are tending towards agree. "Teachers in private sector has less time spend with family" ranks 7th, with mean score of 2.82 and standard deviation 1.51, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards strongly disagreement. The study results were in line with the Jacobsen (2024) explained about the order to give their children the education they need, teachers become selective about the schools. In privatized systems, good schools often cost more. Some teachers send their kids to the same school where they teach. This may afford some form of tuition reduction.

Effect of Privatization on job security and Employment Conditions

Some educators choose to go back to school. They enroll in new courses or participate in retraining programs. The competition among private institutions is a lot higher than in public ones, and acquiring new skills is beneficial. To enhance their chances at getting a job, teachers tend to study online or attend workshops. Balancing work and family can be

quite difficult, but many families with children support each other at this time. Partners might take over household chores while children change their schedule. The primary aim is to obtain new and stable employment for a reliable income in the future (Bray, 2023).

Table 4. Distribution of respondents regarding effect of Privatization on job Security and Employment Conditions of Primary school Teachers

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
Contractual and temporary employment effect job security and employment in privatization	4.26	.90	1
Privatization improved compensation among teachers in private sector	4.17	1.07	2
Increased insecurity with low pay among teachers in private institutes due to privatization	3.99	1.37	3
More Job responsibilities and role flexibility in private sector	3.95	1.26	4
After privatization teachers face lower salaries compared to their counterparts in	3.89	1.24	5

public schools			
Job losses and downsizing effect of job security and employment due to privatization	3.88	1.05	6
Increased pressure on employees to meet targets or goals due to privatization	3.72	1.05	7
Privatization increase flexibility and autonomy in private sector for teachers	3.69	1.12	8
Provide limited training and professional development opportunities for teachers after privatization	2.88	1.69	9

Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

The Table outlines the perceived impact of privatization on job security and employment conditions for teachers, based on mean scores and standard deviations. The findings reveal a complex mix of both benefits and drawbacks resulting from privatization in the education sector. At the top of the list, with a mean of 4.26 and a standard deviation of 0.90, is the strong agreement that "contractual and temporary employment affects job security". The second-highest ranked perception is that, "privatization has improved compensation for some teachers in the private sector" with mean 4.17 and standard deviation 1.07,

indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree.

On the other hand, "increased insecurity with low pay among teachers" with mean of 3.99 and standard deviation 1.37, demonstrating a dual perception: while some teachers benefit from better pay, others experience economic instability and dissatisfaction. Similarly, "more job responsibilities and role flexibility" with mean score 3.95 and standard deviation 1.26, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. Statements regarding "lower salaries compared to public school" counterparts mean 3.89 and standard deviation 1.24, and job losses or downsizing with mean of 3.88 and standard deviation 1.05, indicating that respondents are tending towards agree. "The perception that privatization increases pressure to meet performance targets" with mean of 3.72 and standard deviation 1.05, further supports the narrative of heightened stress and accountability. "While increased flexibility and autonomy in private institutions" was noted with mean of 3.69 and standard deviation 1.12, it ranks lower on the list, suggesting it is either less valued or less consistently experienced across the sector. Finally, "the limited availability of training and professional development opportunities" received the lowest rating (mean = 2.88 and standard deviation 1.69), pointing to a significant gap in teacher support and career growth in privatized environments.

The study results were same as Yin (2023) who stated that employment insecurity is one of the main physiological effects of privatization on families. Job losses can often be immediate when public services are privatized, particularly for those in lower-level or union-protected positions. Teachers, healthcare professionals, and transportation employees, for example might be laid off or rehired with lower benefits. Significant stress

is brought on by the fear of losing one's job or by actual unemployment.

Psychological and emotional impact of privatization on teachers and their families

System of privatization changes the school system of education and teaching. Public schools focus on the students all aspects of education, that helps them to grow academically, socially and emotionally (Zelnick and Abramovitz 2020).

Table 5 Distribution of respondents regarding psychological and emotional impact of privatization on teachers

Psychological and emotional impact of privatization on teachers	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
Lower job satisfaction and decreased motivation among teachers	4.18	.99	1
Burnout and emotional exhaustion increase due to privatization	4.08	.98	2
No control over their work conditions due to privatization	3.77	1.30	3
Leading to disengagement from the profession due to privatization	3.76	1.26	4
Increased stress and anxiety due to policies of privatization	3.52	1.31	5
Privatization effect feelings of disempowerment	3.44	1.39	6

and frustration among teachers			
Leaving the teaching field due to privatization	2.82	1.50	7

Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

The Table presents findings on the psychological and emotional impact of privatization on teachers, ranked according to the mean scores and standard deviation of the respondents. These insights reflect how shifts in employment structures due to privatization affect educators' mental well-being and professional engagement. The highest-rated concern is the "experience of lower job satisfaction and decreased motivation" with a mean of 4.18 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.99, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. This suggests that many teachers feel less fulfilled and less driven in privatized educational environments, likely due to increased pressure, instability, or lack of autonomy. Closely following is "the perception that burnout and emotional exhaustion have increased due to privatization" with means of 4.08 and standard deviation 0.98, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree.

"The lack of control over work conditions" ranks 3rd, with mean score of 3.77 and standard deviation 1.30, indicating that respondents are generally lying between neutral and agree but tending towards agree. This loss of autonomy contributes to the fourth-ranked concern: "disengagement from the profession" with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation 1.26, implying that some educators may emotionally detach from their roles, even if they remain in them. Increased stress and anxiety due to privatization policies scored 3.52, pointing to the broader emotional toll of performance pressures, job insecurity,

and unclear expectations. "Teachers also reported feelings of disempowerment and frustration" with mean score of 3.44 and standard deviation 1.39, which, although slightly lower in rank, are significant in understanding emotional well-being. Interestingly "The lowest-ranked concern was leaving the teaching field entirely due to privatization" (mean = 2.82 standard deviation 1.50), suggesting that while many are emotionally and psychologically strained, not all are prepared or able to leave the profession.

The study results were same as Thoburn (2023) who explained that it is impossible to underestimate the impact on emotions that privatization has taken on families. The loss of social safety nets, increased living expenses, and job insecurity all contribute to an unstable and fearful environment. Due to their inability to balance their role as providers with their diminishing resources, adults frequently take the emotional toll. Depression, anxiety, and in severe cases, substance abuse, are often the results of this emotional stress. This emotional toll does not spare children. Behavior changes such as aggression, withdrawal, or poor grades can result from seeing their parents in distress.

Psychological and Emotional impact of Privatization on Teacher's Families

Family structure changes are frequently due to the of financial strain brought on by privatization. Extended family members may need to live together in order to split living costs. A program like this might offer short-term respite, it also exacerbates domestic conflict and crowding, which has detrimental effects on mental and physical health. Due to their regular trips away from home, parents who work multiple jobs to make ends meet are inclined to become emotionally separated from their children. Such difficult circumstances also raise the likelihood of marital stress and breakdown, which further

weakens the family. When public support systems are eliminated, single-parent households which are already under stress find it even more difficult to handle Nguyen *et al.*, (2023).

Table 6. Distribution of respondents regarding psychological and emotional impact of privatization on teacher's families

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
Teacher's family reduced social interaction due to privatization	4.07	1.16	1
Relationship strain in the society due to privatization	3.91	1.31	2
Increased anxiety and stress among family members due to privatization	3.75	1.34	3
In private sector teacher's families increased family expectations	3.75	1.17	3
Privatization has the holistic impact on family identity and expectations	3.68	1.21	4
Privatization badly impact on children's emotional well-being	3.61	1.29	5
Due to	2.18	1.39	6

privatizing scheme risk for mental health issues increased among family members			
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Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

The data presented in the table highlights the social and emotional impact of privatization on teachers' families. Among the most significant concerns is the "reduction in social interaction experienced by teachers' families" which ranked highest with a mean score of 4.07 and standard deviation 1.16, indicating that respondents are generally tending towards agree. The second major concern, with a mean of 3.91 and standard deviation 1.31, is the "strain on relationships within society caused by privatization" ranked 2nd. This may be linked to the social pressure and comparison between teachers in public and private sectors, potentially creating feelings of inferiority or social isolation. Additionally, "increased anxiety and stress among family members, and rising expectations from teachers by their families" both with a mean score of 3.75 highlights the strong agreement with respondents. Families may expect more financial support or academic success, assuming that the private sector offers better opportunities, without considering the added pressure placed on teachers.

Further, the data indicates that "privatization is perceived to have a holistic impact on family identity and expectations" with a mean of 3.68 and standard deviation 1.21. This suggests that the shift in employment structure changes how families view their roles and long-term goals, possibly aligning more with competitive, outcome-based values. Children's emotional well-being is also reported to be negatively affected by privatization with mean of 3.61 and standard

deviation 1.29, hinting at the indirect psychological consequences of the professional stress teachers experience at home. Interestingly, "the risk of mental health issues among family members" received the lowest agreement with mean of 2.18 and standard deviation 1.39, suggesting that while respondents recognize emotional and social strains, they may not fully associate these with more serious psychological outcomes.

The results were same as Del Tufo *et al.* (2023) who mentioned that Privatization also has an influence on gender dynamics within the family. Because they are typically the ones who provide care, women are frequently the ones who suffer the most when public services are cut. Women may be forced to quit their jobs in order to care for their children if there is no longer access to affordable childcare. Due to social isolation and the loss of their professional identity, this not only leads to them to lose cash but also has an adverse effect on their mental health. But if men are unable to fulfill our traditional roles, they may experience feelings of inadequacy and emotional strain due to the increased pressure to provide. As roles and responsibilities are renegotiated under pressure, these shifting patterns can result in conflict within the family.

Strategies adopted by teachers and their families in response to privatization

Levit (2023) said that students may suffer a variety of consequences from outsourcing schools or giving control to private organizations, especially in terms of their social and emotional development. The focus may shift from students' emotional well-being to their academic performance when schools are run by private organizations. This may prevent students who need help with their relationships or emotions from getting it. Strong school communities are essential for

healthy social development, and privatization may weaken these bonds.

Table 7. Distribution of respondents regarding strategies adopted by teachers and their families in response to privatization

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank order
Teachers and their families must adapting to a more modest lifestyle after privatization in private sector	4.20	1.00	1
Teachers and their families should creating a flexible lifestyle after privatization	3.89	1.26	2
Teachers and their families should manage their finances carefully due to privatization	3.88	1.24	3
Strengthening community and social support necessary in private sector	3.80	1.18	4
Teachers must seek alternative employment due to privatization	3.73	1.28	5
Teachers should set boundaries between work and personal life due to privatization	3.68	1.19	6

Teachers and their families should seek additional sources of income to mitigate the effects of lower wages	3.67	1.11	7
Teachers must manage their time and prioritization due to privatization of school	3.56	1.35	8
Teachers should exploring career transitions in private sector due to privatization	3.55	1.23	9
Due to privatization teachers and their families should cut back on luxuries life	2.85	1.57	10

Scale:1) Strongly Disagree 2) Disagree 3) Undecided 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree

The data provided outlines various coping strategies and adjustments that teachers and their families are compelled to adopt due to the privatization of the education sector, particularly in the private school context. The highest-rated statement, with a mean score of 4.20 and standard deviation 1.00 indicates a strong agreement that "teachers and their families must adapt to a more modest lifestyle" post-privatization.

Closely following this, respondents agreed that "creating a flexible lifestyle" with mean of 3.89 and "managing finances carefully"

with mean of 3.88 are essential coping mechanisms. These responses suggest that teachers are not only aware of their changing financial reality but are also actively considering or implementing practical adjustments to sustain their households. Further, "the need for strengthening community and social support" with mean = 3.80 and standard deviation 1.18, ranks 4th, implies that privatization may isolate teachers from traditional support systems, increasing the need for collective networks or peer communities to manage emotional and financial challenges.

Statements such as "seeking alternative employment" with mean of 3.73 and standard deviation 1.28, "setting boundaries between work and personal life" with mean of 3.68 and standard deviation 1.19, and "finding additional income sources" with mean of 3.67 and standard deviation 1.11, reflect that respondents are generally tending towards agree. These coping responses reveal how privatization compels teachers to consider significant lifestyle and career shifts to maintain household stability. Lower on the scale, though still notable, are the suggestions that "teachers manage time" and "explore career transitions" with mean scores of 3.56 and 3.55, respectively, which highlight the strain on professional development and work-life balance in privatized environments. The lowest-ranked item, "cutting back on a luxurious lifestyle" with mean of 2.85, suggests that respondents either do not consider their previous lifestyle to be "luxurious," or they believe that such measures have become so normalized that they are not seen as a new adaptation. In summary, these results point to the fact that privatization has a major impact on teachers' professional environment and also affects their family dynamics, financial planning, and long-term decisions in significant ways. The strong consensus on adaptive lifestyle strategies indicates a widespread recognition

of these changes

and an increasing demand for institutional backing and policy measures to mitigate their effects.

The study results were same as Fargion (2023) who said that the most effective approach is to create strong protective rules for private institutions. It is essential for the government to also impose basic operational policies when it permits the establishment of private hospitals, schools, or even businesses. Basic guidelines should be established to protect the rights of employees. For instance, private school educators should be entitled to a set minimum salary, maternity leave, and employment stability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Governments and private education providers should ensure that primary school teachers receive competitive salaries and access to benefits, including healthcare, pensions, and paid leave.

Privatized schools should offer more stable employment contracts, minimizing reliance on short-term or contractual positions. Providing teachers with long-term job security will help alleviate anxiety related to employment uncertainty and allow them to plan for their future and the welfare of their families.

Schools should create a supportive work culture that recognizes the hard work and dedication of teachers. Encouraging collaboration among staff, providing mental health resources, and offering counseling services.

Government bodies must ensure that privatized educational institutions are held to high standards regarding teacher welfare.

Teachers should be empowered with representation through unions or professional associations that advocate for their rights and well-being.

Policymakers should consider integrating family welfare programs into the broader

education policy. These programs might include subsidized childcare, educational scholarships for teachers' children, and housing assistance, which directly benefit teachers' families and ease their financial burdens.

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